

Power deposition in the He bath induced by the Z gradient coil in the 11.7T Iseult magnet: theory versus measurements

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Abstract. Gradient-magnet interactions increase with higher field magnets and stronger gradient coils. Perhaps the most sensitive aspect is magnet quench, which can be induced by a loss of superconductivity of the main coil caused by a rise of the temperature of the He bath with gradient activity. Predicting power depositions thereby can be a very valuable tool to avoid dangerous frequency zones but also eventually correct design flaws. In this work, we report model predictions compared to measurements of power deposition in the He bath of the Iseult 11.7T magnet for the Z gradient coil axis.

1. Introduction

Achieving higher resolutions in MRI with higher SNR [1,2] has motivated the development of more advanced radiofrequency (RF) coils [3], stronger magnets [4-6] and more powerful gradient coils (higher gradient strength and higher slew rate) [7-9]. The interaction between the gradient coil and the magnet however puts higher demands on their design to achieve the desired performance. Aside from artefact imaging problems possibly induced by vibrations and eddy-currents, one very important aspect of this interaction is the power deposition in the He bath, or He boil-off, which if not properly taken into account can lead to hardware damage or even magnet quench. With the first in vivo scans performed in 2023, the Iseult 11.7T scanner to date holds the world record for MRI on humans. It is a whole-body 90 cm wide bore magnet where the main superconducting coil is made of NbTi which is cooled down at 1.8K, where He becomes superfluid. The gradient coil, electronics and scanner console have been provided by Siemens Healthineers (Siemens Healthcare, Erlangen, Germany). Before running any imaging experiment, a careful series of tests covering acoustics, vibrations, power deposition in the He bath and the Magnet Safety System (MSS) was performed, first with a lead tube intended to screen the gradient-

magnet interactions [10]. The field was gradually increased and tests were conducted at 3T, 7T, 10.2T and then at 11.7T to learn as much as possible about the system, gain confidence and above all ensure the safety of the magnet. Despite encouraging data for magnet protection, artefacts in the images were discovered at 11.7T and after further analysis (partly thanks to some of the tools presented in this work), it was decided to remove the lead tube. New gradient-magnet interaction measurements followed, but only after sufficient cryogenics margin in the presence of the lead tube became apparent. Power deposition is one of the most sensitive aspects of the gradient-magnet interactions which, if not properly accounted for, can raise the temperature of the He bath and cause the loss of superconductivity of the main coil. The Iseult cryogenic facility can compensate for 15W of deposited power in addition to the natural losses due to heat convection and radiation. Thanks to its 7000 l of He volume, the enthalpy of the reservoir is large and can sustain 200 W.h of energy before reaching 1.95 K and triggering automatically a slow discharge of the magnet for protection. But despite this safety margin, it remained of tremendous importance to quantify this power deposition to guarantee the safety of the magnet and potentially assess dangerous frequency zones where the gradient coil should not ideally operate.

Gradient-magnet interactions lead to a multi-physical problem. At the source, the gradient coil emits a magnetic field or magnetic vector potential which interacts with the different structures and induces eddy-currents. In the presence of a main magnetic field, Lorentz forces then act on the eddy-currents and cause vibrations, which themselves produce more eddy-currents etc. The oscillating currents circulating in the gradient coil for imaging likewise engender vibrations which can couple mechanically to the other conductors. The problem thus is highly complex and multi-physical [11,12]. The goal of this work is to report a power deposition model corroborated with experimental data acquired on the Iseult magnet at 11.7T. For the Z gradient axis, thanks to the axial symmetry, the model is quasi-analytical up to some approximations and to the point where numbers of frequency, dimensions and material properties need to be entered on a computer. The theory makes use of the theory of vibrating thin shells from NASA, whose fundamental equations have been validated for rockets, submarines and even pipelines [13]. One of the fundamental and key assumptions of our model is that the gradient coil emits an (imperfectly shielded) magnetic vector potential which is not affected by the gradient-magnet interactions, and constitutes the source of the perturbations. Its vibration, measured to be hundreds of μm at the most [14] and thus small compared to the wavelengths at a few kHz, is thus assumed to not perturb the fields. The gradient coil also is assumed to be perfectly decoupled mechanically from the surrounding structures. The vibration of the structures, however, is of paramount importance to compute the electric fields which generate together with the motional electromotive forces, by Joule effect, most of the power deposition in the He bath.

2. Theory

The gradient-system installed in the bore tube of the magnet generates in space a time-varying magnetic vector potential \vec{A}_G which leads to an electric field $\vec{E}_G = -\frac{\partial \vec{A}_G}{\partial t}$ according to Maxwell's equations. There is no scalar potential in the expression of the electric field above in the absence of surface charges, for the Z gradient. This electric field induces eddy currents in the conducting enclosures of the Iseult magnet, i.e. here the cryostat, the thermal shield and the helium vessel described in [5,6]. Their closest parts to the gradient-system are their coaxial inner tubes, schematically symbolised in Figure 1. The \vec{A}_G vector distribution was calculated analytically from the Z gradient coil wire patterns provided by Siemens Healthineers and, as explained above, is assumed not to be disturbed by vibrations. The returned map showed that the electric field was much greater in these inner tubes than in the other conducting parts (flanges, outer tubes) which are thus not considered in the following model. Another calculation showed that the eddy-currents induced in the main superconducting coil were also negligible compared to the ones in the tubes. In order to limit the eddy-current harmful effects, a fourth coaxial tube made of lead was inserted between the gradient-system and the bore tube of the cryostat [10]. It was finally removed because of imaging artefacts [14] and thus is not considered here.

Figure 1. Different cylinders taken into account in the model: outer vacuum chamber (OVC), cryoshield and He vessel. The thicknesses of the shells respectively are 5, 10 and 10 mm. Their lengths parallel to the Z axis respectively are 4.2, 4.1 and 4.1 m.

The electric field arising from the vector potential \vec{A}' of the eddy-currents must be taken into account together with the motional electric field due to vibrations of the conductors submitted to Lorentz

forces in the ambient magnetic field. In addition to the simplification considering only three tubes coaxial with the magnet, the model is valid only for the Z gradient axis in such a way that the whole system is axisymmetric. One thus knows a priori that the eddy-current lines are circles around the common O_Z axis. This is not the case for the X and Y -gradient axes leading to a much more difficult problem which involves electric surface charges through a mechanism similar to that of the Hall effect. In cylindrical coordinates (r, φ, z) , for each tube of mass density ρ and electrical conductivity σ we define:

$$\vec{j} = j(r, z, t)\vec{u}_\varphi \text{ the current density,}$$

$$\vec{A} = A(r, z, t)\vec{u}_\varphi \text{ the magnetic vector potential,}$$

$$\vec{B} = B_r(r, z, t)\vec{u}_r + B_z(r, z, t)\vec{u}_z \text{ the magnetic field,}$$

$$\vec{\delta} = \delta_r(r, z, t)\vec{u}_r + \delta_z(r, z, t)\vec{u}_z \text{ the displacement vector,}$$

$$\vec{V} = \frac{d\vec{\delta}}{dt} \text{ the velocity vector.}$$

The displacement amplitudes are small enough so that all quantities in the equations are evaluated at their original position in a fixed reference frame. Their dependence on the radial coordinate r is thus ignored. The current density variation in the tube thickness (skin effect) is taken into account which is not done for the displacement components (“thin shell” approximation) as written above. One can then write:

$$\vec{A} = \vec{A}_G + \vec{A}',$$

$$\vec{B} = \vec{B}_0 + \vec{B}_G + \vec{B}',$$

$$\vec{B}_0 = B_{0r}(r, z)\vec{u}_r + B_{0z}(r, z)\vec{u}_z.$$

The magnetic fields \vec{B}_G of the gradient and \vec{B}' of the eddy currents are several orders of magnitude smaller than the main field of the Iseult magnet \vec{B}_0 and are thus neglected too from now on. There are two partial differential equations (PDEs) for each tube which read:

$$\vec{j} = \sigma \left(-\frac{\partial \vec{A}}{\partial t} + \vec{V} \times \vec{B} \right), \quad (1)$$

$$\rho \left(\frac{d^2 \vec{\delta}}{dt^2} + \omega_0^2 \vec{D} \cdot \vec{\delta} \right) = \vec{j} \times \vec{B}, \quad (2)$$

where $\omega_0 = \frac{1}{a} \sqrt{\frac{E}{\rho(1-\nu^2)}}$ is the fundamental frequency (E is the Young modulus, ρ the mass density, ν

the Poisson ratio and a the radius of the cylinder) and $\overline{\overline{D}}$ contains the Donnell-Mushtari (DM) differential operator [13] further described in appendix. While the first equation comes from basic electromagnetism, the second one relies on the theory of vibrating thin shells, when the distance between the two curved surfaces is small compared to the other distances, here the thickness of the tubes being about 1-2 % the radius of the cylinders. The material is also assumed to be linearly elastic, homogeneous and isotropic. Equation (2) thereby represents Newton's law applied to each elementary element of the tubes with internal forces and moments conveyed by the DM operator, while the term on the right hand side naturally remains the external, Lorentz, force. The derivation of the DM operator is quite involved as it incorporates strain-displacement equations of the three-dimensional theory of elasticity in orthogonal curvilinear coordinates. The reader is invited to consult a more specialized monograph such as [13] for more details. The bar over $\overline{j \times \vec{B}}$ stands for the average over the tube thickness. For a forced harmonic regime at angular frequency ω one has for a linear system:

$$A_G(r, z, t) = A_G(r, z)e^{i\omega t},$$

$$j(r, z, t) = \hat{j}(r, z)e^{i\omega t},$$

$$\vec{\delta} = (\widehat{\delta}_r(z)\vec{u}_r + \widehat{\delta}_z(z)\vec{u}_z)e^{i\omega t},$$

where $\hat{j}(r, z)$, $\widehat{\delta}_r(z)$ and $\widehat{\delta}_z(z)$ are complex amplitudes (phasors). We consider the magnetic field vector potential arising from the gradient coil as the source of perturbations, generated itself by the imposed currents circulating in the gradient coil. As mentioned above, for simplicity we consider such currents unaffected by the gradient-magnet interactions. The Gradient Power Amplifier (GPA) and its Proportional Integrated Derivative setting compensate for current perturbations [9]. Mechanical decoupling between the gradient coil and the magnet, here is sought by means of Sylodyn pads (Getzner, Bürs, Austria). This approximation is discussed further in the paper.

In this regime, the PDEs for each tube become:

$$\hat{j} = -i\omega\sigma(A_G + \widehat{A}' + B_{0z}\widehat{\delta}_r - B_{0r}\widehat{\delta}_z), \quad (3)$$

$$\left(-\frac{\omega^2}{\omega_0^2} + \overline{\overline{D}}\right) \begin{bmatrix} \widehat{\delta}_r \\ \widehat{\delta}_z \end{bmatrix} = \frac{1}{\rho\omega_0^2} \begin{bmatrix} B_{0z}\hat{j} \\ -B_{0r}\hat{j} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (4)$$

They are written in such a way as to isolate on the right-hand side the coupling terms between the electric and the mechanical degrees of freedom. Inductive coupling between the tubes is mediated through \widehat{A}' . Solving for the PDEs yields the displacement complex amplitudes as well as the current densities in

each tube, from which various magnetic quantities such as e.g. the spherical harmonics expansion of their magnetic field for instance can be deduced for field perturbation analysis, which furthermore led to further confidence that the previously installed lead tube was responsible for some of the image artefacts mentioned above. Power deposition can then be obtained by integrating $\frac{|j(r,z)|^2}{2\sigma}$ within the He vessel tube (Joule effect). The appendix provides more details about how to solve the PDEs. The current density in the He vessel hence returned as the solution of these equations is the result of the eddy-currents engendered by the time-dependent fields (themselves originating from eddy-currents in the other cylinders or from the imperfectly shielded gradient coil) and vibration of the He vessel.

3. Methods

Measurements were performed on the whole-body Iseult 11.7T magnet equipped with the SC72 whole-body gradient coil (weight = 900 kg, length = 1.59 m, inner diameter = 64 cm, outer diameter = 81 cm, maximum gradient strength = 70 mT/m and maximum slew rate = 200 mT/m/ms) commercialized by Siemens Healthineers. The Iseult superconducting coil is immersed in a pressurized He bath, which is cooled down to 1.8K. To reach and maintain this temperature, a cryo facility pumps the He gas. The speed of the pumping unit varies depending on the power deposition to maintain a constant temperature. However, the correlation between this speed and the power delivered is not trivial. As a result, for the measurements it was decided to maintain the pumping speed constant, thus the cooling power, and impose a constant 10W power with a heater embedded in the He bath. The 10W power then is compensated by the cooling unit to reach equilibrium. This was achieved by means of a proportional integral regulator to maintain constant temperature, which beforehand was calibrated and tuned with an additional test heater mimicking the power deposition originating from the gradient activity. Figure 2 illustrates the setup.

Figure 2. Experimental setup devised to measure the power deposition in the He bath. Temperature is maintained with a PI regulator which adjusts the power dissipated in one heater so that the sum with the power induced by the gradient activity is 10W. A test heater was used for tuning and calibrating the PI regulator.

When the temperature of the bath is disturbed, the power of the heater adjusts automatically to regulate temperature and maintain it constant. Therefore, one can deduce the power deposition with the gradient fields from the change of power dissipated by the heater. But while the 7000 l volume of helium and the 1.8 K temperature in the Iseult magnet provide a large safety buffer for exploitation, on the other hand it requires time-consuming gradient frequency sweeps to cover a large frequency range and obtain the desired helium boil-off spectra, which can be demanding for the gradient coil and gradient cables as well. For this reason, the measurements presented here employed a sweep rate of 50 Hz/hour and focused on the frequency interval 1300-2000 Hz over which the main cryogenic peaks could be detected in some previous work [14,15]. For the theoretical predictions, calculations were run at fixed frequencies every 1 Hz using optimized routines in Fortran.

To inspect some of the simplifying assumptions made in our model, we also measured vibrations with mono-axial accelerometers (Brüel & Kjaër, Naerum, Denmark) located on the flange of the gradient, at the bottom, along the Y (Antero-Posterior) direction. Gradient sweeps on the Z gradient coil axis were operated on the scanner console over the 0-3 kHz frequency range in a 2 min interval and at 1 mT/m and accelerations were returned with Fourier analysis. Steps at every Tesla during a ramp-up of the magnetic field from 0 to 11.7T were made to perform such measurements, and study the dependence of the vibrations with the B_0 field. For a linear harmonic oscillator, if the currents in the

gradient coil were unaffected despite increased vibrations with B_0 , and if mechanical coupling did not complicate its mechanical behavior, vibrations should increase linearly with field strength according to the Lorentz force. Likewise, because of the importance of vibrations in power deposition results, strong mechanical coupling between the gradient tube and the magnet should result in power deposition peaks at the gradient tube mechanical resonance frequencies.

4. Results

Figure 3.a reports the power deposition measurement, normalized for the maximum gradient strength compatible with the available slew rate (200 mT/m/ms) (shown in Fig 3.b), along with the theoretical prediction computed from our model. Measurement results were low-pass filtered and scaled quadratically with the gradient strength values shown in Fig. 3.b. The apparent offset in the measurements below 1700 Hz can be due 1) to the finite accuracy of our method, 2) remaining mechanical coupling between the gradient coil and the cryostat (mechanical resonances of the gradient coil visible at 1350 Hz and 1550 Hz in Figure 4.a, not taken into account in our model) and 3) disturbance of the gradient shielding efficiency when it undergoes strong vibrations. At equilibrium, without gradient activity, the cryofacility compensates the 10W dissipated in the heater within approximately 0.1W of accuracy, which is then multiplied by our normalization function and then possibly introducing an offset. Our model predicted with reasonable accuracy the position of the largest peaks, yet with roughly a factor of 3 underestimation for the highest one around 1850 Hz. Its breadth also could not be reproduced in the model, perhaps because of lack of mechanical damping in the model as well. The peaks located around 1750 Hz however show an excellent match. The calculation was repeated with no vibrations, i.e. with $B_0 = 0$, and returned at the most power depositions on the order of 10 mW, thereby highlighting the importance of vibrations in this problem. Calculations without the shielding of the gradient coil were also repeated and returned an amplification by more than 10 000 fold of the most dominant peak, emphasizing the importance of the shield but also perhaps the sensitivity of the results on the actual experimental conditions.

Figure 3. Power deposition results at 11.7T with the SC72 Z axis gradient coil. a) Measurements versus theory with results normalized to maximum gradient strength compatible with slew rate (shown in b). Power deposition varies with the square of the amplitude so that the slew rate limit (200 mT/m/ms) enforces a strong apodizing function on the results but reflects the worst-case scenarios given the hardware limits. The 1400-1450 Hz and 1650-1700 Hz intervals in the measurements were skipped due to time constraints but no significant power deposition could be found previously in these frequency zones.

Figure 4.a presents the vibration or acceleration spectra measured on the gradient coil when pulsing at 1 mT/m on the Z gradient axis versus frequency and main field strength (color coding), with the most intense peak located at around 1350 Hz. As expected, vibrations increase with the B_0 field. Figure 4.b reports the height of the 1350 Hz peak versus B_0 , normalized by the one obtained at 1T, which reveals a very linear behavior with the main field strength. A small deviation towards higher fields can be due to increased interactions [11] or simply perhaps the neighboring peak at 1550 Hz spilling over the one located at 1350 Hz. The different widths of the peaks possibly varying with field strength, two neighboring peaks indeed can overlap and make the peak height analysis not as direct. This linear behavior yet could be observed only when 3rd order shim coils were disconnected, a sub-linear evolution having been characterized for that particular resonance when they are connected [14,15].

Figure 4. Vibration measurement results of the gradient coil when pulsing on the Z axis at 1 mT/m. a) Acceleration spectra versus B_0 and frequency. b) Height of the 1350 Hz main peak versus main field strength, normalized to the value measured at 1T.

5. Discussion and conclusion

We have presented an analytical model describing the magneto-mechanical physics of the different structures involved in gradient-magnet interactions to calculate the power deposition in the He bath of the Iseult magnet at 11.7T. Although part of the theory is inspired from the theory of thin shells of NASA focusing on the description of free eigenmodes, we could not find equivalent results for the case of forced harmonic oscillations mixing all mode contributions. Taking vibrations into account turned out to be of great importance. One weakness in our model however is the lack of mechanical coupling between the different vibrating shells and with the gradient coil. Figure 4 yet showed that the gradient coil vibrations increase linearly with the B_0 field strength, when the 3rd order shim coils are disconnected, suggesting that the simple Lorentz force drives the motion of the gradient coil itself and that it is not disturbed by further interactions. Despite this observation, we cannot rule out possible mechanical coupling between the gradient tube and the cryostat, propagating up to the He vessel, while Figure 3.a indeed vaguely suggests residual mechanical coupling giving rise to small peaks at 1350 and 1550 Hz. With our theory, we could predict reasonably well the position of the main cryogenic peaks, yet with an underestimation of roughly a factor 3 compared to the measured data for the most intense peak at 1850 Hz, but with excellent match for the peaks around 1750 Hz. This discrepancy is comparable to other works trying to quantify with software also He boil-off at 10.5T [12]. The mechanical coupling described above, in addition to the approximations made, disturbance of the shielding efficiency of the gradient coil, mechanical damping, nonlinearities and uncertainties in the material properties used

throughout, could explain some of the differences. The main mechanical resonance at 1350 Hz of the gradient tube in Fig. 4.a also is not visible in the power deposition spectrum of Fig 3.a which, given the importance of vibrations on the results, suggests that our mechanical decoupling assumption is reasonably valid. Yet it is also clear ~~also~~ that our model (Figure 3.a) could not reproduce the breadth of the main peak observed experimentally around 1850 Hz. Likewise we could ascertain with the same theoretical model that the dominant peaks could be greatly amplified in the absence of the shielding coil. As a result, it appears reasonable that uncertainties in its fabrication or deformations of its circuit with vibration could play a role too.

Given so little experimental and theoretical data available on the topic of gradient-magnet interactions, it could appear to us premature to entirely rely on commercial multi-physical numerical codes. The complexity of the problem is high, while expert committees are still active to benchmark computational electromagnetic tools alone (e.g. <https://www.compumag.org/wp/team/>) [16]. As a result, we chose to adopt in this work analytical approaches with thoroughly validated textbook results and derivations, but whose downsides naturally are their limits in complexity. Future work would indeed include the use of advanced numerical codes but whose first step could be their validation with our model under the same simplifying assumptions. If good agreement between the two could be found, one could consider then progressively increase the complexity of the problem with more confidence. With lack of a gold standard, it is the authors' hope that the proposed model can already provide some insights and help guiding magnet-gradient designs, e.g. by pushing power deposition resonances towards higher frequencies or by detecting potential flaws.

The linear behavior of the vibrations versus B_0 , in contradiction with Lorentz damping [11], at least up to 11.7T, was not observed in some other works [14,15] on the same system when the 3rd order shim coils were connected. The cryogenic results of Figure 3.a here were obtained with the 3rd order shim coils disconnected. They were repeated with the coils connected and returned drastically different power deposition results (data not shown) [15]. Disconnecting them at the filter plate inside the Faraday cage presumably opens their corresponding loop circuit so that current can no longer circulate, thereby minimizing their impact. It remains to investigate how they can yield such drastically different behaviors when they are connected, which is the subject of further work. These results therefore were not presented here to match better our modeling attempts, which ignored the influence of the 3rd order shim coils. The results however emphasize that incorporation of these shim coils is of great importance for accurate modeling of the gradient-magnet interactions if they are connected and used.

The Z gradient axis yielding the strongest interactions in our setup [14], the data of Fig. 3.a shows that under these conditions, MR scans could be operated on Iseult for approximately 3.5 hours at 100 % duty cycle, at maximum gradient strength (shown in Fig. 2.b) and at the single worst frequency

thereby reaching 60 W of power deposition, before running into the 200 W.h limit. This scenario fortunately is unrealistic in practice and with more realistic duty cycles and MRI acquisitions, as a result we do not anticipate any cryogenic problem in the exploitation of Iseult with the gradient coil currently in place. Thanks to the large He reservoir, in any case the temperature rise induced by the gradient coil activity is slow. The system therefore can detect potentially risky sequences and shut them down to stop power deposition instantaneously. The limits however would have to be revisited with repeated measurements if a more powerful head-gradient coil was to be installed.

In conclusion, we have presented a theory and experimental data about power deposition in the He bath at 11.7T in the Iseult MRI system. It concludes a long series of gradient-magnet interaction tests with the whole-body SC72 gradient coil which were necessary to establish a safe operation for the magnet. Although interesting phenomena arose from these investigations (e.g., vibrations, impact of 3rd order shim coils etc) which are not yet totally understood, at this stage the gradient-magnet interactions do not constitute an immediate threat for the Iseult 11.7T whole-body magnet. The authors hope with these efforts to contribute to acquire a better understanding of the gradient-magnet interactions and help making predictions.

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7. Appendix : Vibrations and induced currents in the conducting structures of a superconducting MRI magnet

The objective of this appendix is to provide more details about an analytical model for a configuration justifiably limited to the coaxial tubes of the magnet. A separate calculation showed that the power deposition induced in the superconducting coil itself as well as on the flanges (the disks perpendicular to the Z axis and thus to the tubes) were negligible compared to the one generated on the tubes, which is thus one approximation we make. The flanges yet remain of importance for the boundary conditions of the vibrations (no radial displacement at the extremities). The only analytical approach which is possible is for the Z gradient axis thanks to its inherent axial symmetry. The presented derivations are not meant here to be exhaustive but rather to provide the general philosophy of the approach. The

interested reader can find more material in some specialized textbooks addressing vibrations [13], elasticity [17] and electromagnetism [18].

We start from Equations (3) and (4) of the paper. There are three tubes considered: the He vessel, the cryoshield and the Outer Vacuum Chamber (OVC or bore tube). The lead tube initially inserted in the Iseult magnet is not described here. But the same formalism could be applied, yet with different boundary conditions for this specific tube. Thus for the He vessel, the cryoshield and the OVC we have for a linear system at fixed angular frequency ω :

$$\hat{j} = -i\omega\sigma(A_G + \hat{A}' + B_{0z}\hat{\delta}_r - B_{0r}\hat{\delta}_z),$$

$$\left(-\frac{\omega^2}{\omega_0^2} + \bar{D}\right) \begin{bmatrix} \hat{\delta}_r \\ \hat{\delta}_z \end{bmatrix} = \frac{1}{\rho\omega_0^2} \begin{bmatrix} B_{0z}\hat{j} \\ -B_{0r}\hat{j} \end{bmatrix},$$

which describes magneto-mechanical coupling. The coupling between the tubes is mediated via \hat{A}' , i.e. the magnetic potential vector arising from the eddy currents. As a result, it is important to note here another approximation which is to ignore mechanical coupling between the different tubes. The latter, however, can vibrate and such vibration is incorporated in the model.

7.1. Solutions without vibrations

In this case we have $B_0 = 0$ which simply leads to:

$$\hat{j} = -i\omega\sigma(A_G + \hat{A}').$$

The geometrical configuration of the Z gradient coil being known, calculation of A_G is a standard magnetostatics problem given that considering the frequencies of interest (several kHz at the most) and the dimensions of the system, propagation delays are negligible. The expression for the potential vector generated by the eddy currents is:

$$\hat{A}'_Q = \frac{\mu_0}{4\pi} \iiint \frac{\hat{J}_P}{|PQ|} dV_P,$$

where the integral is performed over the volumes of the three tubes, which can be calculated for instance using the method of moments to obtain the final value at point Q. Variation of the current density \hat{j} in the tube must be taken into account both along Z but also with the radius r (skin effect). For that purpose, each tube was discretized into small toroïd sections with rectangular cross section $\Delta r \times \Delta z$ in which we considered the current density constant and equal to the value calculated at the center. We then calculated the inductance of each toroïd as well as their mutual inductances (including with the gradient coil loop wires). To make the calculations more tractable, each elementary toroïd was considered as a thin solenoid whose radius was the average radius of the element, with length Δz and surface current density $\hat{j}\Delta r$. The self and mutual inductances could then be evaluated with high precision by exploiting analytical expressions making use of elliptic integrals. The returned outputs then are \hat{j} , A_G and \hat{A}' by solving the following system of linear equations:

$$\begin{aligned}
A_{G,ik} &= C_{ik}I_0, \\
\widehat{A}'_{ij} &= C'_{ij}\widehat{J}_j, \\
\frac{i}{\omega\sigma_i}\widehat{J}_i - \sum_j C'_{ij}\widehat{J}_j &= \sum_k C_{ik}I_0 \quad \forall i,
\end{aligned}$$

where I_0 is the amplitude of the current circulating in the gradient coil, i and j are the indices of the elements of the tubes and k the index of the elements of the gradient coil. The C_{ik} and C'_{ij} coefficients arise from the self and mutual inductance calculations with the elliptic integrals mentioned above.

7.2. Thin-shell vibrations

Let $h = a_2 - a_1$ be the thickness of the tube, $a = \frac{1}{2}(a_1 + a_2)$ its average radius and $2b$ its length, the tube being symmetric with respect to the median plane xOy of the magnet and the Z -gradient coil. If $h \ll a$ (thin-shell approximation), for small vibrations the displacement vector does not depend on the radial coordinate r within the tube, unlike for the current density (skin effect). In these conditions, the main part of the $\overline{\overline{D}}$ operator is known as the Donnell-Mushtari (DM) operator and one can associate to it the Flügge modification. The necessary parameters for the shells are the density ρ , the Young modulus E and the Poisson coefficient ν . With $\omega_0 = \frac{1}{a}\sqrt{\frac{E}{\rho(1-\nu^2)}}$ the fundamental angular frequency, $k = \frac{e^2}{12a^2}$ the thickness parameter (e being the the thickness), $\overline{\overline{\delta}}(s = \frac{z}{a}, t) = \begin{bmatrix} \delta_r(s, t) \\ \delta_z(s, t) \end{bmatrix}$ the displacement vector, we have:

$$\overline{\overline{D}} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 + k \frac{\partial^4}{\partial s^4} & \nu \frac{\partial}{\partial s} \\ -\nu \frac{\partial}{\partial s} & -\frac{\partial^2}{\partial s^2} \end{bmatrix} + k \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -\frac{\partial^3}{\partial s^3} \\ \frac{\partial^3}{\partial s^3} & 0 \end{bmatrix},$$

where the second term on the right hand side of the equation is the Flügge modification. Boundary conditions can be set for the displacements δ_r and δ_z , the axial force N_z , the axial torque M_z and the so-called Kirchhoff's force S_z at the extremities of the tubes ("shear-diaphragm" boundary conditions). With flanges, they become $\delta_r = 0$, $N_z = 0$, $M_z = 0$ so that at the extremities we have

$$\begin{aligned}
\delta_r &= 0, \\
\left(\nu - k \frac{\partial^2}{\partial s^2}\right) \delta_r + \frac{\partial \delta_z}{\partial s} &= 0, \\
-\frac{\partial^2 \delta_r}{\partial s^2} + \frac{\partial \delta_z}{\partial s} &= 0.
\end{aligned}$$

If these boundary conditions are set at both extremities, symmetric with respect to the medial plane xOy , the equations can be exactly fulfilled with the following expressions:

$$\begin{aligned}
\widehat{\delta}_r &= \left(\sum_{m=1}^{\infty} R_m \sin \frac{m\pi z}{b}\right) e^{i\omega t}, \\
\widehat{\delta}_z &= \left(\sum_{m=1}^{\infty} Z_m \cos \frac{m\pi z}{b}\right) e^{i\omega t},
\end{aligned}$$

for each of the 3 tubes in the Iseult magnet.

7.3. Vibration eigenfrequencies

In the absence of external forces we have:

$$\sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \left(-\frac{\omega^2}{\omega_0^2} + \bar{D} \right) \begin{bmatrix} R_m \sin \frac{m\pi a}{b} s \\ Z_m \cos \frac{m\pi a}{b} s \end{bmatrix} = 0,$$

$$\bar{D} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 + k \frac{\partial^4}{\partial s^4} & v \frac{\partial}{\partial s} \\ -v \frac{\partial}{\partial s} & -\frac{\partial^2}{\partial s^2} \end{bmatrix} + k \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -\frac{\partial^3}{\partial s^3} \\ \frac{\partial^3}{\partial s^3} & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

Setting $\lambda_m = \frac{m\pi a}{b}$ and $\Omega = \frac{\omega}{\omega_0}$, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} (-\Omega^2 + 1 + k\lambda_m^4 + k)R_m - (v\lambda_m + k\lambda_m^3)Z_m &= 0, \\ -(v\lambda_m + k\lambda_m^3)R_m + (-\Omega^2 + k\lambda_m^2)Z_m &= 0, \forall m = 1, 2, \dots \end{aligned}$$

When written in matrix form, the determinant of the matrix must be 0 to obtain non trivial solutions:

$$(-\Omega_m^2 + \lambda_m^2)(-\Omega_m^2 + 1 + k\lambda_m^4 + k) - (v\lambda_m + k\lambda_m^3)^2 = 0, m = 1, 2, \dots$$

The above equation returns the normalized frequencies $\Omega_m = \frac{\omega_m}{\omega_0}$ of the vibration eigenmodes. The thickness parameter k for $h = 6$ mm and $a = 500$ mm returns $k = 1.2e-5$. Neglecting the corresponding contributions highlighted in red and blue by setting $k = 0$ constitutes the membrane approximation. Further analysis in our case shows that the Flügge modification (in blue) indeed has no influence and therefore can be dropped. The fourth derivative contributions ($k\lambda^4$) in the DM operator on the other hand must be conserved. Even in this case, when m becomes relatively large, the DM operator may lack accuracy so that one may attempt regaining accuracy by using a heuristic approach consisting of fitting the effective values of the contributions of the operator ($f_m = 1 + k\lambda_m^4$ and $g_m = \lambda_m^2$) to the known exact eigenfrequencies of a tube that can be computed, with additional efforts, using the equations of elasticity.

7.4. Forced harmonic vibrations

In the case of a forced harmonic regime at frequency ω , the partial differential equations contain terms with dependence on z which likewise can be expressed as Fourier series, as expressed above for $\widehat{\delta}_r$ and $\widehat{\delta}_z$. If the excitation frequency is equal to one of the resonance frequencies, the solution naturally diverges if damping is not incorporated. It is yet not necessary here to introduce such mechanical damping as the electromagnetic coupling results in somewhat equivalent damping effects, which prevent the solutions from diverging.

7.5. Full solution incorporating vibrations and electromagnetism

We return to the initial partial differential equations which are for each tube:

$$\hat{j} = -i\omega\sigma(A_G + \hat{A}' + B_{0z}\hat{\delta}_r - B_{0r}\hat{\delta}_z),$$

$$\left(-\frac{\omega^2}{\omega_0^2} + \bar{D}\right) \begin{bmatrix} \hat{\delta}_r \\ \hat{\delta}_z \end{bmatrix} = \frac{1}{\rho\omega_0^2} \begin{bmatrix} \overline{B_{0z}\hat{j}} \\ -\overline{B_{0r}\hat{j}} \end{bmatrix},$$

The coupling terms for the first electric and the two mechanical equations through the B_0 field are indicated in red. Still ignoring the Flügge contribution in the operator \bar{D} , the system of equations to solve is:

$$\hat{j} = -i\omega\sigma(A_G + \hat{A}' + B_{0z}\hat{\delta}_r - B_{0r}\hat{\delta}_z),$$

$$(1 - \Omega^2)\hat{\delta}_r + k\frac{\partial^4\hat{\delta}_r}{\partial s^4} + \nu\frac{\partial\hat{\delta}_z}{\partial s} = \frac{1}{\rho\omega_0^2}(\overline{B_{0z}\hat{j}}),$$

$$\nu\frac{\partial\hat{\delta}_r}{\partial s} + \Omega^2\hat{\delta}_z + \frac{\partial^2\hat{\delta}_z}{\partial s^2} = \frac{1}{\rho\omega_0^2}(\overline{B_{0r}\hat{j}}).$$

By decomposing again the displacements into Fourier series (truncation here to M terms):

$$\hat{\delta}_r = \sum_{m=1}^M \hat{R}_m \sin \frac{m\pi z}{b},$$

$$\hat{\delta}_z = \hat{Z}_0 + \sum_{m=1}^M \hat{Z}_m \cos \frac{m\pi z}{b},$$

and with $\lambda_m = \frac{m\pi a}{b}$ and $\Omega = \frac{\omega}{\omega_0}$, we get:

$$-i\frac{\hat{j}}{\omega\sigma} + \hat{A}' + \sum_{m=1}^M B_{0z}\hat{R}_m \sin \frac{m\pi z}{b} - \sum_{m=0}^M B_{0r}\hat{Z}_m \cos \frac{m\pi z}{b} = -A_G,$$

$$\sum_{m=1}^M [(-\Omega^2 + 1 + k\lambda_m^4)\hat{R}_m - \nu\lambda_m\hat{Z}_m] \sin \frac{m\pi z}{b} - \frac{1}{\rho\omega_0^2}(\overline{B_{0z}\hat{j}}) = 0,$$

$$\Omega^2\hat{Z}_0 + \sum_{m=1}^M [\nu\lambda_m\hat{R}_m + (\Omega^2 - \lambda_m^2)\hat{Z}_m] \cos \frac{m\pi z}{b} - \frac{1}{\rho\omega_0^2}(\overline{B_{0r}\hat{j}}) = 0.$$

The first of the three equations above involves all the discretized elements of all tubes because of the \hat{A}' term, while the two following ones lead to two equations per tube. Truncation of the Fourier series is done to limit the number of terms while keeping reasonably accurate results with a convergence analysis.

7.6. Practical details in the current implementation

The magnet, the tubes and the Z gradient coil considered in this work have cylindrical symmetry. They are coaxial and aligned with the Z axis and symmetrical with respect to the median plane xOy . The currents in the gradient coil are antisymmetric with respect to the same plane. The Figure 5 reports the discretization principle for the tubes.

Figure 5. Modeling and discretization details for the three tubes considered in the theoretical work (outer vacuum chamber, cryoshield, He vessel).

Symmetry considerations allow sparing the calculation of some unknowns, by considering the currents and the displacements located for $z > 0$. For the coupling between elements however, both regions in space must be taken into account. The tubes above are labeled 1, 2 etc, starting the further away from the z axis going through the isocenter. In our case tube 1 is the He vessel. Each tube is discretized with toroids with axial axis z and with a rectangular cross section as shown at the bottom of the drawing. The numbers of segments along the z and radial axis for the k^{th} tube are nz_k and nr_k respectively, giving a total number of elements $nt = nz \times nr$ for each tube. After verification of convergence of the results, we chose $h_s = 8$ mm and $e_s = 1$ mm to also limit the number of unknowns and computation time on a standard desktop computer. The total number of elements in this case becomes for the three tubes $nt = nt_1 + nt_2 + nt_3 = 2560 + 2590 + 1315 = 6465$. As explained above, each element is considered to have a (complex) uniform current density \hat{j}_s but the self and mutual inductances are evaluated as if they were pure thin solenoids passing through the centers of the elements (fixed radius r). The unknowns to determine are the nt complex amplitudes of the currents for each segment, i.e. $\hat{I}_s = e_s h_s \hat{j}_s$.

The other unknowns are the complex amplitudes \hat{R}_m and \hat{Z}_m of the displacements. If we choose $M = 40$ for the number of terms in the Fourier series for each tube, we have a total of $240 + 3 =$

243 terms for 3 tubes. They are listed according to the order and labeling of the tubes in the following way:

$$\begin{aligned}
 x_{nt+1} = \widehat{R}_{1,1}, x_{nt+2} = \widehat{Z}_{1,1}, x_{nt+3} = \widehat{R}_{1,2}, x_{nt+4} = \widehat{Z}_{1,2}, \dots, x_{nt+2M} = \widehat{Z}_{1,M}, \text{ (tube 1)} \\
 \dots \\
 x_{nt+4M+1} = \widehat{R}_{3,1}, x_{nt+4M+2} = \widehat{Z}_{3,1}, x_{nt+4M+3} = \widehat{R}_{3,2}, \dots, x_{nt+6M} = \widehat{Z}_{3,M}, \text{ (tube 3)} \\
 x_{nt+8M+1} = \widehat{Z}_{1,0}, x_{nt+8M+2} = \widehat{Z}_{2,0}, x_{nt+8M+3} = \widehat{Z}_{3,0}.
 \end{aligned}$$

This way a total number of 8021 equations with 6708 unknowns is written in matrix form. We utilized the “zgelss” and “zgesv” routines from LAPACK to solve the problem.

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